

Wessobrunn Prayer (Das Wessobrunner Gebet), (Dat gafregin ih mit firahim firiuuizzo)

Modern translation work by Armaan Seth

Schöpfungsgedicht or “Wessobrunn Creation Poem”) is one of the earliest surviving poetic works in Old High German, dating back to the late 8th century.

The poem takes its name from Wessobrunn Abbey, a Benedictine monastery in Bavaria, where the only known manuscript of the text was once housed. After the abbey’s dissolution in 1803, its library was absorbed into the Bavarian Royal Library in Munich, where the manuscript received the catalog number Clm 22053.

The manuscript features a Latin title written in uncial script, followed by the main text in Caroline minuscule. Paleographic evidence indicates that it was produced in Bavaria, displaying certain Swabian influences—suggesting an origin in southern Bavaria, likely within the Diocese of Augsburg.

Although the text is associated with Wessobrunn, it was probably not written there, as the original monastery was destroyed during a Magyar raid in 955. Scholars have proposed several possible sites of origin for the manuscript, including Regensburg, Benediktbeuern, Staffelsee, and Augsburg itself.

Why this piece? Translations of these pieces are impossible to find in full or modern translation in today ever so ever-evolving English.

Extraction

To extract the piece, I started with the image below.

The Wessobrunner Gebet in Clm 22053, online facsimile (digitale-sammlungen.de)

You can see my attempts to extract the piece and work below as well.

Attempt 1

Dat [ga]fregin ih [mi]t firahim firiuiizzo meista, dat ero ni uuas noh ufhimil, noh paum noh pereg ni uuas, ni sterr noh [hein]ig noh sunna ni scein, noh mano ni liuhtra noh der mareo seo.

Do dar niuuiht ni uuas, enteo ni uuenteo, enti do uuas der eino almahtico cot, manno miltisto, enti dar uuârûn ouh manake mit inan, cootlihhe geista enti cot heilac.

Cot almahtico, du himil enti erda gauuorahtos, enti du mannun so manac coot forgapi, forgip mir in dina ganada rehta galaupa enti cotan uuilleon, uuistom enti spahida enti craft tiuflun za uuidarstantanne, enti arc za piuisanne enti dinan uuilleon za gauurchanne.

Attempt 2

Dat **gafregin** ih mit firahim firiuuizzo meista, dat ero ni uuas noh ufhimil, noh paum noh pereg ni uuas, ni sterr nohheinig noh sunna ni scein, noh mano ni liuhta noh der **mareo** seo. Do dar niuuiht ni uuas, enteo ni uuenteo, enti do uuas der eino almahtigo cot, manno miltisto, enti dar uuârûn ouh manake mit inan, cootlihhe geista enti **cot heilac**. **Cot almahtigo**, du himil enti erda **gauuorahtos**, enti du mannun so manac **coot forgapi**, forgip mir in dina **ganada rehta galaupa enti cotan uuilleon**, uuistom enti **spahida** enti craft tiuflun za uuidarstantanne, enti arc za piuuisanne enti dinan uuilleon za **gauurchanne**.

Attempt 3

Dat gafregin ih mit firahim firiuuizzo meista,
dat ero ni uuas noh ufhimil,
noh paum noh pereg ni uuas,
ni sterr nohheinig noh sunna ni scein,
noh mano ni liuhta noh der mareo seo.
Do dar niuuiht ni uuas, enteo ni uuenteo,
enti do uuas der eino almahtigo cot,
manno miltisto, enti dar uuârûn ouh manake mit inan,
cootlihhe geista enti cot heilac.

Cot almahtigo, du himil enti erda gauuorahtos,
enti du mannun so manac coot forgapi,
forgip mir in dina ganada rehta galaupa enti cotan uuilleon,
uuistom enti spahida enti craft
tiuflun za uuidarstantanne,
enti arc za piuuisanne enti dinan uuilleon za gauurchanne.

Defining/Refining

To start to translate the piece, I separated the wording into sections to identify each phrase/word with research. I ended up with the list featured below:

Dat – that

gafregin – have heard (past participle of *fregan*, “to ask, inquire, learn”)

ih – I

mit – among, with

firahim – men, mankind (dative plural of *firiho*)

firiuuizzo – wise man, sage (*firi* = man, *wizzo* = wise)

meista – most (superlative ending)

dat – that

ero – earth

ni uuas – was not (*ni* = not, *uuas* = was)

noh – nor, and not

ufhimil – heaven above (*uf* = over, *himil* = heaven)

noh paum – nor tree (*paum* = tree)

noh pereg – nor mountain (*pereg* = mountain, hill)

ni uuas – was not

ni sterr – nor star (*sterr* = star)

nohheinig – nor any (*heinig* = one, any)

noh sunna – nor sun (*sunna* = sun)

ni scein – shone (from *scīnan*, to shine)

noh mano – nor moon (*mano* = moon)

ni liuhta – gave light (*liuhtan*, to shine, give light)

noh der mareo seo – nor the wide sea (*mareo* = broad, wide; *seo* = sea)

Do – then, at that time

dar – there

niuuht – nothing, naught (*ni-wiht*, “no-thing”)

ni uuas – was not

enteo ni uenteo – no end nor limit (*enteo* = end, *uenteo* = boundary, border)

enti – and

do – then

uuas – was

der eino – the one

almahtigo cot – almighty God (*al-mahtig* = all-mighty, *cot/got* = God)

manno – of men (genitive plural of *man*)
miltisto – most merciful (superlative of *mild*, gentle, merciful)
enti – and
dar uuârûn – there were
ouh – also, too
manake – many (plural of *manag*)
mit inan – with him (*inan* = him, dative/accusative)
cootlihhe geista – goodly spirits (*cootlihhe* = goodly, holy; *geista* = spirits)
enti cot heilac – and holy God (*heilac* = holy, sacred)

Cot almahtigo – Almighty God

du – you, thou

himil enti erda – heaven and earth

gauuorahtos – created, wrought (*ga-wurahhan*, to make, form)

enti du mannun – and you (who) to men (*mannun* = dative plural of *man*)

so manac coot forgapi – so many goods you grant (*manac* = many, *coot* = good, *forgapi* = you give, grant)

forgip mir – give (imperative) me

in dina ganada – in your grace (*ganada* = grace, mercy)

rehta galaupa – right belief (*rehta* = right, true; *galaupa* = faith)

enti cotan uuilleon – and good will (*cotan* = good, *uilleon* = will, desire)

uuistom – wisdom (*wîstom*)

enti spahida – and insight, discernment (*spâhi*, wise, perceptive)

enti craft – and strength, power

tiuflun za uuidarstantanne – to withstand devils (*tiufl* = devil, *uuidar-stantan* = stand against, resist)

enti arc – and evil (*arc* = evil, wickedness)

za piuuisanne – to avoid, to flee (*piuuissan* = to shun, keep away)

enti dinan uuilleon – and your will (*dinan* = your)

za gauurchanne – to accomplish, perform (*ga-wurhhan* = to make, to do)

Some mistakes I made that I researched and corrected: I found that the “uu” is equivalent to “w”. We can interpret that “uwas” means “was.” “Cot” is also a form of “got,” which can be translated to god.

A huge thing I needed to look out for was the infinitives and dative with “za”. And when translating, I realized earlier that the syntax is actually paratactic

Pure, Modern, and Simplified Translations

After 12 drafts, here is what I came down with.

Pure:

I have heard among men, among the wisest of men,
that earth was not, nor heaven above,
nor tree stood, nor mountain rose,
nor star shone, nor sun gave light,
nor moon gleamed, nor the wide sea.

Then there was naught, no end nor border,
and there was the One, Almighty God,
mildest to men; and with Him were also many,
goodly spirits and holy God.

God Almighty, Thou who heaven and earth hast wrought,
and Thou who to men so many goodly gifts grantest,
grant me in Thy grace right faith and good will,
wisdom and wit and might
to withstand the fiend,
to flee evil and to work Thy will.

Modern:

I have heard among men, among the wisest of men,
that once there was neither earth nor heaven above,
no tree stood, no mountain rose,
no star shone, no sun gave light,
No moon gleamed, and the wide sea was not.

Then there was nothing, no end and no boundary,
only the One, Almighty God,
gentlest toward men. And with Him were also many
good and holy spirits, glorious God.

Almighty God, You who have made heaven and earth,
And You who grant so many good gifts to humankind,
grant me by Your grace true faith and goodwill,
wisdom, understanding, and strength
to withstand the evil one,
to flee from sin, and to do Your will.

Simplified:

Among the many men, and the smartest men
They say there was once neither an earth nor a heaven
There were no trees or tall mountains
The star did not shine, and there was no sun to give light
No moon gave light, and no body of water was big

Then there was nothing, without an end or boundary
Appeared was a true, one god, gentle to all men
With him, good and holy spirits came, glorious god

Almighty God, You who have made heaven and earth,
And You who grant so many good gifts to humankind,
grant me by Your grace true faith and goodwill,
wisdom, understanding, and strength
to withstand the impure one,
to flee from evil, and to do your good actions.

Author Notes: Thank you for dedicating your time to reading my translations and my work on Das Wessobrunner Gebet, or the Wessobrunner prayer. I really enjoyed this piece as it struck so powerfully with me. As an 8th-grade student in Gainesville, FL, I spent many hours trying just to extract the text by hand. I usually enjoy working in ethics, law, and moral philosophy. As a debater, I used to wonder what the best way was to express my passion for the subjects. I chose literature might be the route. I started with research, reading (a lot!), writing, speeches that I wish I had given, and then I put my heart in soul into writing a novel. This Novel was dedicated to helping members of society achieve personal growth with relatable connections about moral philosophy(ethics) and law. I called it “Moral,” and it's something I am proud of today. Besides writing a Moral, I wanted to achieve a goal of translating a work of literature and publishing it to bring it to be notice of many. I wanted to choose a piece so unrecognized that it could get the recognition it deserves. This is how I landed at Das Wessobrunner Gebet.